

METHODS OF TREATING ADDUCTOR CONTRACTURE OF THE HIP JOINT IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract. *The results of treatment for 68 patients aged 2 to 18 years with adductor contracture of the hip joint, treated between 2015 and 2025 at the Traumatology and Orthopedics Department of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute (TashPMI) Clinic, were analyzed. Of these, 41 were boys and 27 were girls.*

Keywords: *children, cerebral, palsy methods of treating.*

Introduction. Determining indications for conservative or surgical treatment tactics to address the orthopedic complications of cerebral palsy remains complex due to factors such as the patient's overall condition, multiple components of the hip joint, its anatomical structure, and pathological changes (1-7-5). It should be noted that the treatments administered to these patients do not fully enable normal movement. Rather, these interventions facilitate standing, joint mobility, and self-care activities for the patients.

Cerebral palsy in children (CP) is a polyetiological brain disorder that may arise during fetal development, at birth, or postnatally. CP gradually induces changes in the joints, leading to the development of various contractures, which, from an orthopedic perspective, directly and negatively impact a child's mobility. This condition affects 68% of children with CP [1-3-8]. Pathological dislocations, subluxations, and contractures in the joints complicate an already challenging treatment process and hinder the children's ability to move independently [2-3]. Many authors suggest that adductor contracture of the hip joint arises due to an increase in muscle tone in this area [7-13].

Excessive tone in the adductor muscles of the thigh, combined with reduced tone in the gluteal muscles, disrupts balance and promotes the development of contractures, limiting leg extension. This, in turn, disrupts the centering of the femoral head in the acetabulum, potentially leading to subluxation outside the acetabulum [7-12].

According to some authors, adductor contractures of the hip joint are secondary, with congenital hip dislocation and hip dysplasia accounting for only 0.3–0.5% of cases [3-9]. Globally, the prevalence of these conditions is currently on the rise [7]. Approximately 80% of these patients adapt to life and acquire suitable professions through the use of orthoses and orthopedic devices [4-12]. In the spastic form of cerebral palsy, predicting motor development remains relative and does not serve as a comprehensive guide for neurologists, neurosurgeons, and orthopedists. Currently, predicting disruptions in motor function development is of great importance in determining treatment strategies for this patient category [7-8].

Materials and Methods. To date, conservative methods used to treat spastic unstable hip joints have only proven effective in young children during the early stages of the condition [2]. As the child ages, complications such as spastic instability worsen, leading to hip joint contractures, relative leg shortening, pelvic tilt, and limitations in physical activity. In light of this, authors propose neuro-orthopedic interventions with positive outcomes.

Purpose of the Study: The aim is to achieve positive results by applying the optimal treatment method for adductor contracture of the hip joint in children with cerebral palsy.

The treatment outcomes of 68 patients aged 2 to 18 years with adductor contracture of the hip joint, treated between 2005 and 2025 at the Traumatology and Orthopedics Department of the TashPMI Clinic, were analyzed. Of these, 41 were boys and 27 were girls.

Based on the degree of musculoskeletal system impairment, patients were categorized as follows:

1. Able to walk independently – 17 patients (25.2%).
2. Able to walk with assistive devices – 21 patients (30.8%).
3. Able to stand upright with both hands as support – 22 patients (32.3%).
4. Unable to walk independently – 8 patients (11.7%).

All patients underwent clinical, radiological, and neurological examinations.

Results and discussion. Clinically, patients exhibited impaired walking patterns, joint deformities in the musculoskeletal system, muscle atrophy, difficulty walking, or reliance on assistive devices. Contractures affecting flexion-extension, rotation, and abduction-adduction in the joints directly influenced the patients' overall condition, including cosmetic aspects. Radiological examinations were performed in the anteroposterior projection of the hip joint for all patients, with femoral head decentration observed in 12 cases. X-rays also revealed femoral proximal torsion and an increased neck-shaft angle in 51 patients. Comprehensive neurological assessments were conducted for all patients, enabling accurate selection of conservative or surgical treatment tactics.

Patients with hip joint contractures resulting from cerebral palsy were treated using two approaches: conservative and surgical. Conservative treatment was administered to 46 patients under the age of 6, with an individualized approach at each stage. During conservative treatment, patients received massages, therapeutic exercises to enhance hip joint activity, paraffin therapy, and neurological interventions. After completing the initial physiotherapy stage, 27 patients were fitted with Sheptun-Ter Yegiazarov plaster casts to stretch the legs, gradually widened over time. After three months, the casts were removed, and outpatient treatments continued with orthopedic devices and orthoses. For severe adductor contractures, percutaneous tenotomy of the adductor muscles was performed in 19 patients as part of these interventions. All conservatively treated patients continued outpatient care under supervision.

Surgical treatment was conducted in 22 patients over the age of 6. Of these, 7 underwent detorsion surgery, followed by plaster cast fixation for one month, after which phased physiotherapy and neurological treatments were administered. Orthoses were prescribed to all patients. In 9 patients with severe internal rotation, muscle transposition was performed, followed by detorsion plaster casts for 4 weeks. After removal, subsequent physiotherapy was conducted outpatiently. In cases of severe limitation of leg extension due to adductor contracture, simultaneous muscle transposition and bilateral tenotomy were performed in 8 patients, yielding positive results. Post-surgery, these patients were fitted with orthoses and devices, and appropriate outpatient treatments followed cast removal.

Results: Determining indications for conservative or surgical treatment to address orthopedic issues in cerebral palsy remains complex due to the patient's overall condition, multiple hip joint components, anatomical structure, and pathological changes (14). It should be noted that

these treatments do not fully restore normal movement but enable patients to stand, perform joint movements, and engage in self-care activities.

In most patients, disease progression exacerbates pathological changes in the hip joint, worsening anatomical and functional conditions and complicating treatment. Therefore, thorough examinations and analyses are essential to actively implement appropriate surgical interventions. Indications for surgical treatment are somewhat limited in patients who cannot walk or sit independently. Not all patients seek treatment promptly; for such cases, selecting less invasive soft tissue surgeries is advisable.

At our clinic, surgical interventions such as adductor muscle tenotomy and muscle transposition in the hip joint area are used to eliminate contractures and internal leg rotation in a single stage. This approach saves time and allows for earlier postoperative rehabilitation. These procedures are performed after thoroughly assessing the patient's age, overall condition, type of pathological process, range of motion, and radiological findings, leading to favorable outcomes.

Surgical interventions are carried out with the consultation and approval of neurologists in the operating room, adhering to antiseptic and aseptic protocols. The treatment area is prepared, and the leg is gently extended outward from the hip joint. This tenses the adductor muscles, making them palpable. Using a syringe needle, percutaneous tenotomy is performed on one side, then the other, without cutting the skin, through a small puncture. The patient is then placed prone, and muscle transposition is performed. A diagonal incision is made below the knee toward the proximal side, soft tissues are dissected layer by layer, and the muscles to be transposed are separated from the fascia and secured with sutures. Simultaneously, the musculus semitendinosus is lengthened with 3–4 partial transverse incisions. The musculus gracilis is severed, and its distal end is transposed to the separated portion of the musculus rectus femoris using lavsan thread. After transposition eliminates internal rotation, tissues are sutured layer by layer with atraumatic thread. An aseptic dressing is applied, and torsion orthoses are used for one month.

In our supervised cases, analysis of one severe patient with hip joint contractures revealed suboptimal outcomes, attributed to the family's socioeconomic conditions, inability to access timely postoperative treatments, and failure to use orthopedic devices and orthoses.

Conclusion:

1. Hip joint pathology in cerebral palsy is a widespread orthopedic condition, encompassing both anatomical and functional aspects, requiring a comprehensive approach to diagnosis and treatment.

2. Conservative treatments are appropriate for younger patients, while surgical methods are recommended after age 6.

3. When rapid progression of the pathological process exacerbates contractures, direct surgical intervention can yield positive results, facilitating early restoration of motor functions.

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